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National Army Academy (Lviv, Ukraine), e-mail: annetta000@gmail.com,
ORCID 0000-0002-7292-1605**The Use of English-Language Materials of Cultural Heritage of Ukraine and Library Resources for the Formation of Patriotic and Intercultural Competences of Military University Teachers**

This study examines how English-language materials on Ukraine's cultural heritage and library resources contribute to the development of patriotic and intercultural competences among teachers of military higher education institutions. **Objective.** The purpose of this work is to substantiate and analyse the pedagogical potential of English-language cultural heritage materials and library resources in fostering patriotic and intercultural competences of teachers in military higher education institutions. **Methods.** The paper uses a set of theoretical research methods, including analysis of scientific sources in the field of pedagogy, linguodidactics and cultural studies, generalisation and systematisation of normative documents on language training of teachers, as well as comparison, systematisation, system-structural and system-functional analysis. **Results.** The results of the study have shown that the integration of English-language cultural sources and the possibilities of library collections provides deepening of knowledge about national heritage and the development of the ability to present it in an intercultural context, which contributes to the professional mobility of teachers. **Conclusions.** It is concluded that the systematic involvement of these resources in the educational process of military higher education institutions creates conditions for a harmonious combination of patriotic education with the development of intercultural communication skills, which is an important component of the modern educational paradigm.

Keywords: cultural heritage of Ukraine; English-language materials; library resources; patriotic competence; intercultural competence; teachers; military higher education institutions; foreign language training

Introduction

Ukraine's accession to the European Higher Education Area, reform of the Armed Forces of Ukraine (AFU), deepening of cooperation with NATO, development of international relations in the field of military education, as well as introduction of advanced technologies for the production of military equipment, modern types of weapons, information and logistical support of military operations, creation of an effective system of training military specialists according to modern standards, and establishment of strategic communication in the defence sector necessitate the formation of patriotic and cultural competence. In today's environment, the development of patriotic and intercultural competences of teachers is one of the priority tasks, the solution of which will ensure not only their effective professional activity, but also the education of future officers with a strong civic position, values and the ability to intercultural communication in the international military environment.

Of particular importance in this context is the use of English-language materials of Ukraine's cultural heritage and library resources, which are an important tool for integrating national identity and global experience. Their involvement allows us to simultaneously address

the tasks of patriotic education and the development of intercultural competence, as familiarity with Ukrainian cultural heritage in English opens up wide opportunities for communication in the international professional environment and representation of Ukraine on the world stage.

In the scientific literature, the problem of forming patriotic and intercultural competences has been considered in the works of many Ukrainian researchers (O. Ilchenko, D. Zadorozhnyi, Y. Kolodka, V. Yahupov, etc.), who focused on the role of foreign language education and cultural approach in professional training. Considerable attention was also paid to the study of the possibilities of library resources as an educational tool (A. Huraliuk, T. Zhalko, etc.). For example, Y. Kolodka focused on identifying methodological principles and approaches, key ideas and provisions on the basis of which the development of intercultural competence of the AFU officers takes place, which is important in the context of Ukraine's Euro-Atlantic integration, expansion of cooperation with NATO member states and participation in multinational operations (Kolodka, 2025). Some researchers also considered the role and place of higher education institution libraries as information centres in the process of foreign language learning, including in military institutions, in a number of publications. For example, the publication by A. Zhukova makes a significant contribution to understanding the transformation of university libraries into multifunctional information centres that actively support foreign language learning. The author analyses how modern academic library goes beyond its traditional role as repository of printed materials and becomes dynamic educational hub that provides access to digital resources, electronic databases, and interactive learning environments (Zhukova, 2024).

At the same time, the issue of the integrated use of English-language materials of Ukrainian cultural heritage and library resources in the system of higher military education under martial law remains insufficiently studied.

The purpose of this paper is to substantiate and analyse the pedagogical possibilities of using English-language materials of Ukrainian cultural heritage and library resources to develop patriotic and intercultural competences of teachers of military higher education institutions.

Methods

The study used an integrated approach that combined theoretical methods aimed at substantiating the possibilities of using English-language materials of the cultural heritage of Ukraine and library resources to develop patriotic and intercultural competences of military teachers of higher education institutions. Thus, the analysis of scientific sources in the field of pedagogy, linguistics and cultural studies made it possible to identify current trends in the development of intercultural communication and patriotic education in military education. Generalisation and systematisation of normative documents on language training of teachers, scientific sources were used to determine the theoretical, methodological and applied aspects of the problem of forming the competences of military university teachers. Comparison, systematisation, system-structural and system-functional analysis were used to determine the content and structure of patriotic and intercultural competencies of teachers at military higher education institutions.

Results and Discussion

In today's international security environment, when global challenges require countries to cooperate as much as possible in the military sphere, the formation of patriotic and intercultural competence of military higher education teachers is becoming a critical element of military personnel training. Today, teachers of military higher education institutions must not only have

professional competence and military skills, but also be patriotic, morally strong, responsible for the lives of students, capable of making quick decisions in critical situations, able to ensure public safety, intercultural interaction, etc. Only such specialists will be able to educate a worthy generation of military personnel, future officers who will possess such qualities as civic responsibility, patriotism, ethical behaviour, as well as the ability to communicate effectively at all levels of the military hierarchy, work in a team, and perform their duties professionally.

Nowadays, there are many methods, tools and technologies for developing various competences of military university teachers. In this study, we will consider the use of English-language materials of the cultural heritage of Ukraine and library resources for the development of patriotic and intercultural competences of teachers, but first of all, we will focus on the concepts of “patriotic competence of a military university teacher” and “intercultural competence of a military university teacher”.

Thus, the problem of patriotic education is of particular importance in today’s conditions, because the future of our nation largely depends on its solution. Patriotic education has a clear goal – to prepare military education students for the defence of the Motherland and is an integral part of the system of ensuring the national security of Ukraine. According to O. Ilchenko and D. Zadorozhnyi, military service is an important element in ensuring national security, so patriotism and civic responsibility should be key aspects in the training of officers. The formation of these qualities contributes to the awareness of future officers of their role in the defence of Ukraine’s sovereignty and independence; the development of patriotic feelings helps to foster in future officers a sense of pride of their country and responsibility towards its citizens (Ilchenko & Zadorozhnyi, 2024).

In this regard, teachers in military HEIs should have patriotic competence. We interpret the patriotic competence of a military higher education institution teacher as an integrative quality of a personality that combines a system of national values, in-depth knowledge of the history and cultural heritage of Ukraine, and a willingness to instil in cadets a sense of love for the Motherland, responsibility for its future and readiness to defend the state. This competence is manifested in the ability of a teacher to form strong patriotic beliefs in military personnel, prepare them to fulfil their civic and constitutional duties, motivate them to self-sacrifice and serve society in the face of modern challenges, as well as help future military personnel inherit the spiritual and cultural heritage of the Ukrainian people and achieve a high culture of relationships. In addition, the patriotic competence of a military university teacher involves the formation of patriotic consciousness and self-awareness, military and professional orientation in cadets in order to ensure their undoubted readiness for the quality performance of military duty to serve the Motherland.

Regarding the concept of “intercultural competence of a military university teacher”, scholars V. Yahupov and Y. Kolodka note that the “intercultural competence of officers is their professionally important mental formation that characterises theoretical and practical preparedness, ability and readiness as a subject of the operational level of military management for intercultural interaction with representatives of different cultures” (Yahupov & Kolodka, 2024).

O. Vasylenko notes that the structure of intercultural competence of officers consists of three main components: cognitive – knowledge about native and other cultures, understanding of cultural differences and awareness of one’s own cultural identity, intrapersonal – personal qualities that facilitate intercultural interaction, including empathy, tolerance and openness to new experiences, interpersonal (behavioural) – skills and abilities to communicate and interact effectively with representatives of other cultures, including behaviour adaptation to meet the needs of the other culture. The researcher also defines the principles of intercultural competence development, including: openness, adaptability, reflexivity (Vasylenko, 2022).

In our opinion, the intercultural competence of a military university teacher is the ability of a teacher to communicate effectively and adequately with representatives of other cultures, taking into account their values, beliefs and behavioural norms. It implies openness, tolerance, the ability to adapt the educational process to the intercultural context, as well as the ability to develop intercultural communication skills in cadets, which are necessary for performing tasks in international military and peacekeeping cooperation. Thus, the intercultural competence of military university teachers includes not only knowledge of cultural differences, but also an awareness of military diplomacy, international humanitarian law and strategies of interaction in military conflicts. This competence involves the development of stress resistance, the ability to make decisions in crisis situations and the observance of clear subordination during intercultural interaction. The intercultural competence of military university teachers plays a significant role in preparing future officers for service in multinational military contingents, peacekeeping missions and international cooperation programs, and its development is a key element in improving the effectiveness of military education in today's globalised world.

The development of intercultural competence of teachers in the military environment has a number of peculiarities, as it is not only the general erudition of a person that is important, but also the ability to quickly adapt to new conditions and interact with other military units in stressful situations, as well as cooperate with foreign partners. In addition, it is necessary to take into account the specifics of military culture, which in many countries has its own rituals, traditions and standards of behaviour (Kolodka, 2025).

We believe that it is important to use English-language materials of the cultural heritage of Ukraine and library resources to develop the patriotic and intercultural competences of military higher education teachers. Thus, the use of English-language materials of the cultural heritage of Ukraine is an effective tool for the development of both patriotic and intercultural competences of military university teachers. Firstly, the use of authentic sources in English on Ukrainian history, literature, art, architecture and traditions enables teachers to better understand the meaning of national identity and values. Working with such materials helps them to develop a sense of pride in Ukrainian culture, understanding its contribution to world civilisation, and increases their willingness to pass this knowledge on to cadets in the context of fostering patriotism and national identity. Secondly, learning about Ukraine's cultural heritage through English-language texts contributes to the development of intercultural competence, as it allows teachers to integrate Ukrainian cultural discourse into the global educational space, present it to foreign colleagues, and participate in international scientific and professional discussions. Thirdly, the use of English-language materials stimulates the development of intercultural communication skills, as teachers learn to explain Ukrainian traditions, historical events and cultural phenomena with a view to foreign language and multicultural audiences, which is important in international military cooperation and peacekeeping. Thus, the systematic introduction of English-language sources related to the cultural heritage of Ukraine not only deepens the patriotic convictions of military university teachers, but also broadens their professional outlook, forming the ability to act effectively in a multicultural environment.

The use of library resources is also an effective tool for the development of patriotic and intercultural competences of military higher education teachers, as the library is not only a traditional source of knowledge, but also a modern information centre that provides access to a wide range of printed, electronic and multimedia materials.

As A. Huraliuk rightly notes, nowadays the library of a higher education institution in Ukraine is an open communication system that participates in pedagogical, educational, intercultural, interlibrary exchange, as well as in exchange with internal structures of the institution (departments, household services, museums, public organisations) and other public institutions

(schools, publishing houses, technical schools). The library's communication activities are aimed at creating a comfortable environment for using information; forming institutionalised and using non-institutionalised channels and means of interpersonal communication and knowledge exchange; developing means of internal organisational and external information links (Huraliuk, 2024).

Libraries currently play a special role in the educational process, because as the main social institutions engaged in the collection, storage and provision of socially useful information, they form information resources, which are generally a concentrated array of documented information that communicates knowledge from all areas of society (Zhalko & Liashuk, 2023).

Library collections, which include scientific works, reference books, fiction and journalism, and English-language sources on the cultural heritage of Ukraine, allow teachers to better understand the cultural and historical context of national identity and integrate it into their professional activities. An important aspect is also access to electronic databases, international catalogues and resources that provide an opportunity to compare national experience with foreign practices, contributing to the development of intercultural awareness and the ability to build effective communication in a multinational military environment. Organising library exhibitions, thematic discussions, presentations, roundtables and trainings at libraries allows teachers to receive not only information but also practical skills in working with materials of cultural value. This integration of library resources into the professional development of military higher education teachers contributes to the formation of patriotic competence through an awareness of the historical role of Ukrainian culture and statehood, as well as intercultural competence through the acquisition of tolerant communication skills, understanding of cultural diversity and readiness to cooperate in an international context. In general, the library becomes a valuable innovative space for the formation of value guidelines, strengthening patriotic principles and broadening the intercultural outlook of teachers, ensuring their readiness for effective teaching and educational activities in military higher education institutions.

Conclusions

Thus, summarising the results of the study, we can state that the formation of patriotic and intercultural competences of teachers of military higher education institutions is a strategic task of modern military pedagogy, which has a direct impact on the quality of training of future officers and strengthening of Ukraine's defence capabilities. The use of English-language materials of Ukraine's cultural heritage and library resources in this process is an effective tool that combines patriotic education with the development of intercultural communication skills. This approach contributes to a deeper understanding of national identity and historical and cultural values, and significantly expands the possibilities of integration into the international educational and military space. Libraries and English-language cultural sources open up new methodological horizons for teachers, enabling them to effectively combine scientific, educational and cultural resources to develop cadets' patriotic feelings and readiness to serve the Motherland, as well as intercultural interaction skills in multinational military contingents. In the future, the results of this study can become the basis for the development of innovative curricula, the creation of electronic educational resources and platforms that integrate cultural heritage into military education, as well as for the implementation of a system of professional development for military university teachers focused on combining patriotic consciousness with intercultural competence. This will ensure the training of highly qualified specialists who are able to act effectively in today's globalised and unstable world.

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Використання англомовних матеріалів культурної спадщини України та бібліотечних ресурсів для формування патріотичної і міжкультурної компетентностей викладачів військових ЗВО

У даному дослідженні розглядається, як англомовні матеріали про культурну спадщину України та бібліотечні ресурси сприяють розвитку патріотичних та міжкультурних компетентностей серед викладачів військових вищих навчальних закладів. **Мета.** Метою даної роботи є обґрунтування й аналіз бібліотечних ресурсів та педагогічного потенціалу англомовних матеріалів про культурну спадщину у формуванні патріотичних та міжкультурних компетентностей викладачів військових вищих навчальних закладів. **Методика.** У роботі використовується комплекс теоретичних методів дослідження, зокрема аналіз наукових джерел у галузі педагогіки, лінгводидактики та культурології, узагальнення та систематизація нормативних документів щодо мовної підготовки викладачів, а також порівняння, систематизація, системно-структурний та системно-функціональний аналіз. **Результати.** Результати дослідження показали, що інтеграція англомовних культурних джерел та можливості бібліотечних фондів забезпечують поглиблення знань про національну спадщину та розвиток здатності презентувати її в міжкультурному контексті, що сприяє професійній мобільності викладачів. **Висновки.** Зроблено висновок, що систематичне залучення цих ресурсів до освітнього процесу військових вищих навчальних закладів створює умови для гармонійного поєднання патріотичного виховання з розвитком навичок міжкультурної комунікації, що є важливою складовою сучасної освітньої парадигми.

Ключові слова: культурна спадщина України; англомовні матеріали; бібліотечні ресурси; патріотична компетентність; міжкультурна компетентність; викладачі; військові заклади вищої освіти; навчання іноземних мов

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